

Synthesis and characterization of mixed ligand complexes of Mn^{II} with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and salicylaldehyde, substituted salicylaldehyde, hydroxy aryl ketones or β -diketones

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Abstract : A series of mixed ligand complexes of Mn^{II} of the type [MnLL'(H₂O)₂], (where HL = 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and HL' = salicylaldehyde, 5-bromosalicylaldehyde, 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxyacetophenone, 2-hydroxypropionophenone, 2-hydroxybenzophenone, pentane-2,4-dione, 1-phenylbutane-1,3-dione or 1,3-diphenylpropane-1,3-dione) have been synthesized by 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratios of manganese(II) acetate with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and above mentioned ligands. The resulting complexes have been characterized by elemental analyses, conductances, IR and FAB mass spectral studies. The *in vitro* antibacterial studies of the ligands and the metal complexes have also been carried out. The complexes have been found to be more potent bactericides than the ligands. Octahedral geometry has been proposed for the prepared mixed ligand complexes.

Keywords : Mixed ligand complexes, 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde, manganese(II) acetate, FAB mass, IR spectra, antibacterial studies.

Introduction

The chemistry of manganese in various oxidation states is currently receiving much attention of investigators owing to its importance in many areas essential to superoxide dismutase and azide insensitive catalase¹.

Mixed ligand complexes play an important role in various biological processes, as exemplified by many instances in which enzymes are known to be activated by metal ions^{2,3}. Such complexes have been implicated in the storage and transport of active substances through membranes⁴. Many mixed ligand complexes are finding applications in the microelectronic industry, chemical vapour deposition of metals and as drugs^{5,6}. Aromatic *o*-hydroxyaldehydes readily enter cyclization and are therefore important synthetic precursors of carbocyclic and heterocyclic compounds. For example, 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde is widely used for preparing various luminophores, optical whiteners^{7,8}, analytical reagents⁹ and drugs¹⁰.

Kalechits *et al.*¹¹ synthesized 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde under condition of heterogeneous catalysis. A number of Schiff bases, derived from condensation

of various amines with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde, have been widely prepared and investigated by various spectral and analytical methods¹²⁻¹⁵ and also by single crystal X-ray diffraction¹⁶.

Narang *et al.*¹⁷ have reported Fe^{II}, Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde oxaldihydrazone and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde malondihydrazone. A series of Schiff base complexes have been synthesized by the condensation of 1,2-diaminocyclohexane with salicylaldehyde, 2-pyridinecarboxaldehyde and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde with manganese, cobalt, copper and iron salts by Lu and co-workers¹⁸. A new series of four mixed ligand complexes of oxo-peroxomolybdenum(VI) of the general composition, [MoO(O₂)(2-hnd)(L)].H₂O, where 2-hndH = 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and LH = *o*-acetoacetanilide, *o*-acetoacetotoluidide, acetylacetone or methyl acetoacetate, has been synthesized by Maurya *et al.*¹⁹. A series of Ru^{III} Schiff base complexes have been reported by Mahalingam *et al.*²⁰ where Schiff bases are derived from the condensation of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde with aniline, 4-chloroaniline, 2-methylaniline and 4-methoxyaniline.

Earlier, mixed ligand complexes of Co^{II} with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde have been reported from our laboratory^{21,22}. In the present paper mixed ligand complexes of the type $[\text{MnLL}'(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$, (where HL = 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and HL' = salicylaldehyde, 5-bromosalicylaldehyde, 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxyacetophenone, 2-hydroxypropiophenone, 2-hydroxybenzophenone, pentane-2,4-dione, 1-phenylbutane-1,3-dione or 1,3-diphenylpropane-1,3-dione) are reported.

Experimental

Chemicals : 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (Fluka), 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde (Aldrich), 5-bromosalicylaldehyde (Aldrich), 2-hydroxybenzophenone (Aldrich), 1-phenylbutane-1,3-dione (Sisco-chem), 1,3-diphenylpropane-1,3-dione (Sisco-chem) were purified by recrystallization from hot ethanol. Salicylaldehyde (Merck), 2-hydroxyacetophenone (John Baker), 2-hydroxypropiophenone (Fluka), pentane-2,4-dione (K. Light) and *n*-butanol were purified by distillation before use. $\text{Mn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Fluka) was used as supplied.

Analytical methods and physical measurements : Manganese was determined volumetrically by EDTA titration using Eriochrome Black T as an indicator²³. Nitrogen was determined by Kjeldahl's method. Specific conductances were measured at room temperature in DMSO by a digital conductivity meter-NDC-736. Carbon and hydrogen analyses were carried out on a Heraeus Carlo Erba 1108 instrument. Infrared spectra (KBr) of the complexes were recorded in the region 400–4000 cm^{-1} on a Nicolet Magna-550 FTIR spectrophotometer. The FAB mass spectra were recorded on a JEOL-SX102/DA-600 mass spectrophotometer/Data system using Argon/Xenon (6 kV, 10 mA) as the FAB gas. The accelerating voltage was 10 kV and spectra were recorded at room temperature. *m*-Nitrobenzyl alcohol was used as the matrix.

Antibacterial bioassay (in vitro) : Five of the ligands named salicylaldehyde, 5-bromosalicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxyacetophenone, 2-hydroxypropiophenone and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and four of the newly prepared corresponding mixed ligand complexes of manganese $[\text{Mn}(\text{hnp})(\text{sal})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$, $[\text{Mn}(\text{hnp})(5\text{-Brsal})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$, $[\text{Mn}(\text{hnp})(\text{hap})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ and $[\text{Mn}(\text{hnp})(\text{hpp})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ were

screened *in vitro* for their antibacterial activity against Gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC-29213) and Gram-negative bacteria *Escherichia coli* (ATCC-25922) using Muller Hinton agar by well diffusion method^{24,25}. The bacterial strains grown on nutrient agar at 37 °C for 18 h, were suspended in a saline solution (0.85% NaCl) and adjusted to a turbidity of 0.5 MacFarland standard Colony forming units (10^8 CFU/ml). The suspension was used to inoculate 90 mm diameter petri plates. Wells (6 mm diameter) were punched in the agar with the help of a sterile metallic borer. Recommended concentration (100 μL) of the test extract (5 mg/ml in DMSO) was introduced in the respective wells. Other wells supplemented with reference antibacterial drug ciprofloxacin (5 mcg) served as positive control. The dissolution of the organic extracts (methanol) was aided by DMSO, which did not affect the growth of microorganism in accordance with control experiments, behaved as negative control. The plates were incubated in air at 37 °C for 24 h. Antibacterial activities were evaluated by measuring inhibition zone diameters.

Synthesis of mixed ligand complexes of manganese(II) : To the butanolic solution (~10 ml) of $\text{Mn}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (8.160 mmol, 2.0 g), a butanolic solution (~25 ml) of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (8.159 mmol, 1.405 g) and butanolic solution (~25 ml) of salicylaldehyde (8.156 mmol, 0.995 g) were added with constant stirring on a magnetic stirrer in a round bottom flask. The above reaction mixture was stirred for about one hour. The pH of the reaction mixture was raised up to ~8.0 by the addition of 5% aqueous sodium hydroxide solution drop wise with continuous stirring. About 10 ml of sodium hydroxide was required to attain the desired pH. The pH was measured with the help of a pH paper and stirring was continued for about five to six hours. The resulting mixture was kept in the refrigerator for two days. The solid separated was filtered, washed with butanol and later with petroleum ether and dried under reduced pressure.

A similar procedure was adopted for the synthesis of mixed ligand complexes of Mn^{II} with 5-bromosalicylaldehyde, 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxyacetophenone, 2-hydroxypropiophenone, 2-hydroxybenzophenone, pentane-2,4-dione, 1-phenylbutane-1,3-dione or 1,3-diphenylpropane-1,3-dione and 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde.

Results and discussion

The reaction of manganese(II) acetate tetrahydrate with 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and salicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxyacetophenone, 2-hydroxypropiophenone or 2-hydroxybenzophenone in 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratios result in the formation of mixed ligand complexes (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1. Synthesis of mixed ligand complexes of Mn^{II}.

Similarly, the other mixed ligand complexes (Scheme 2) were synthesized with 5-bromosalicylaldehyde or 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde.

Scheme 2

The mixed ligand complexes were obtained as Scheme 3 with pentane-2,4-dione, 1-phenylbutane-1,3-dione or 1,3-diphenylpropane-1,3-dione.

where R¹ = -CH₃, R² = -CH₃, R¹ = -CH₃, R² = -C₆H₅; R¹ = -C₆H₅, R² = -C₆H₅

Scheme 3

The resulting complexes are yellow to brown colored solids. All the complexes decompose on heating at high temperature. They are insoluble in chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, benzene, nitrobenzene and methanol or most of the organic solvents but soluble in DMSO.

Molar conductances : The molar conductivity measurements were made in DMSO solution (10⁻³ M). All the complexes show molar conductivity in the range 13.7–42.4 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹. The molar conductivities indicate that all the metal complexes are non electrolytes²⁶ in nature, indicating that the anions are directly coordinated to the metal ion.

Infrared spectra : The ligand 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde, used in the present investigation contains two donor sites : (i) the carbonyl oxygen and (ii) the phenolic oxygen. The infrared spectra of free 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde shows three spectral bands at 3060, 1630 and 1520 cm⁻¹ assignable to ν(OH) (strongly intramolecular hydrogen bonded with carbonyl oxygen), ν(C=O) and ν(C-O) (phenolic), respectively. When phenolic oxygen coordinates with the metal center after deprotonation, ν(OH) (phenolic) observed at 3060 cm⁻¹ in the free ligand, should disappear in the infrared spectra of all the complexes. In fact, this band has been found to disappear in all the complexes, suggesting the coordination of phenolic oxygen after deprotonation¹⁹. In free salicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxyacetophenone, 2-hydroxypropiophenone, acetylacetone, benzoylacetone and dibenzoylmethane bands at 1680, 1660, 1650, 1724, 1724 and 1806 cm⁻¹ respectively have been reported due to ν(C=O)²⁷. In the IR spectra of Mn^{II} mixed ligand complexes, strong absorption bands in the region 1650–1598 cm⁻¹ may be attributed to coordination ν(C=O). Thus, the shifting of ν(C=O) to lower wave number in the mixed ligand complexes supports the coordination of C=O group of the ligand to the metal atom. Mane and co-workers²⁸ have reported similar bands due to ν(C-O) at 1610 and 1617 cm⁻¹ in Mn^{II} complexes with Schiff bases derived from 3-acetyl-6-methyl-(2*H*)-pyran-2,4(3*H*)dione and 3-chloroaniline and 3-aminophenol.

In the mixed ligand complexes, the new weak to medium intensity bands appeared in the region 450–420 cm⁻¹, which are absent in the free ligands, may be assigned to νM–O vibration. Similar peaks are assigned by Lal *et al.*²⁹ and Murukan and Mohanan³⁰.

Bands in the region 1540–1500 cm⁻¹ in the complexes may be attributed to ν(C=C). A broad band appeared at 3500–3100 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned to ν(OH) of coordinated water molecules. Similar bands are observed in the region 1556–1512 and 3500–3300 cm⁻¹ respectively for ν(C=C) and ν(OH) of the coordinated water molecules by Agrawal *et al.*³¹.

Fast atom bombardment mass spectra : Mass spectra of complexes [Mn(hnp)(hnp)] (I), [Mn(hnp)(bzac)] (II), [Mn(hnp)(5-NO₂sal)] (III) and [Mn(hnp)(5-Brsal)] (IV) have been recorded and the spectrum of [Mn(hnp)(bzac)] is reproduced in Fig. 1. The *m/z* values of the peaks and their relative abundance with respect to base peak are shown in Table 2. Complexes I, II, III and IV exhibit base peak at *m/z* 154, 226, 176 and 176 respectively. The matrix peaks may appear at *m/z* 136, 137, 154, 289, 307 in the absence of any metal ion. A peak is observed due to molecular ion [Mn(hnp)(hnp)]⁺ at *m/z* 375, [Mn(hnp)(bzac)]⁺ at *m/z* 387, [Mn(hnp)(5-NO₂sal)]⁺ at *m/z* 391 and [Mn(hnp)(5-Brsal)]⁺ at *m/z* 426 for complex I, II, III and IV respectively. Molecular ion peak of complex II is much intense as compared to other com-

plexes. Complex IV shows a peak at *m/z* 346 due to the loss of bromide moiety from the molecular ion [M]⁺.

In addition, peaks due to the corresponding symmetrical bis-complexes MnL₂ and MnL'₂ are also observed as a result of the redistribution reactions.

For example, peak at *m/z* 397 has been noticed for all the complexes due to Mn(hnp)₂⁺ ion. Peaks due to Mn(hnp)₂⁺, Mn(bzac)₂⁺, Mn(5-NO₂sal)₂⁺ and Mn(5-Brsal)₂⁺ have been observed in complex I, II, III and IV respectively.

In all the complexes, peaks are also observed due to the formation of MnL⁺ and MnL'⁺ species, as a result of the loss of one or the other ligand moiety.

A peak is seen at *m/z* 226 due to Mn(hnp)⁺ for all the complexes. In case of complex II and III peak due to such ion is interestingly most abundant. The peaks corre-

Fig. 1. Mass spectrum of [Mn(hnp)(bzac)].

Table 1. Characterization data for the mixed ligand complexes of Mn^{II} complex

Sl. no.	Complex molecular formula, molecular weight	Colour (% yield)	Decomposition temp. (°C)	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)				Molecular conductance (Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹)
				Mn	C	H	N	
1.	[Mn(hnp)(sal)(H ₂ O) ₂] C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₆ Mn, 383.024	Brown (65.44)	206	13.33 (14.34)	55.82 (56.39)	3.91 (4.21)	-	15.6
2.	[Mn(hnp)(5-Brsal)(H ₂ O) ₂] C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₆ MnBr, 461.92	Yellow (81.39)	204	11.82 (11.89)	46.23 (46.76)	2.87 (3.27)	-	17.2
3.	[Mn(hnp)(5-NO ₂ sal)(H ₂ O) ₂] C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₈ MnN, 428.003	Brown-yellow (95.85)	206	12.50 (12.83)	48.22 (50.47)	3.26 (3.53)	3.202 (3.27)	42.4
4.	[Mn(hnp)(hap)(H ₂ O) ₂] C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₆ Mn, 397.041	Brown (92.19)	185	12.87 (13.84)	56.77 (57.43)	4.23 (4.57)	-	19.8
5.	[Mn(hnp)(hpp)(H ₂ O) ₂] C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₆ Mn, 411.058	Yellow-brown (58.99)	210	12.83 (13.36)	56.58 (58.39)	4.62 (4.90)	-	31.9
6.	[Mn(hnp)(hbp)(H ₂ O) ₂] C ₂₄ H ₂₀ O ₆ Mn, 459.062	Yellow (67.60)	208	11.05 (11.97)	61.59 (62.74)	3.77 (4.39)	-	31.8
7.	[Mn(hnp)(acac)(H ₂ O) ₂] C ₁₆ H ₁₈ O ₆ Mn, 361.038	Yellow (88.42)	175	14.42 (15.22)	52.93 (53.18)	4.88 (5.02)	-	18.3
8.	[Mn(hnp)(bzac)(H ₂ O) ₂] C ₂₁ H ₂₀ O ₆ Mn, 423.059	Yellow-green (95.17)	165	12.50 (12.98)	58.11 (59.57)	4.64 (4.76)	-	15.2
9.	[Mn(hnp)(dbzm)(H ₂ O) ₂] C ₂₆ H ₂₂ O ₆ Mn, 485.080	Yellow (79.91)	160	10.91 (11.32)	64.01 (64.32)	4.22 (4.52)	-	13.7

sponding to MnL'⁺, which would have resulted by the loss of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde moiety are observed in the complexes, e.g. peak at *m/z* 204 due to Mn(hpp)⁺, at *m/z* 216 due to Mn(bzac)⁺ at *m/z* 221 due to Mn(5-NO₂sal)⁺ and at *m/z* 255 due to Mn(5-Brsal)⁺ are observed for complex **I**, **II**, **III** and **IV** respectively.

Formation of various oligomeric species can be explained with the help of the following reactions.

In some cases peaks due to such oligomeric ions are less intense whereas few peaks are quite abundant, e.g. in complex **I** at *m/z* 601 (5.56%), **II** at *m/z* 613 (80.56%), **III** at *m/z* 618 (8.57%) and in **IV** at *m/z* 652 (9.72%) due to Mn₂L₂L'⁺, whereas peaks due to Mn₂LL'⁺ are observed at *m/z* 579 (0.28%), 603 (61.11%), 613 (5.71%) and 681 (16.67%) in complex **I**, **II**, **III** and **IV** respectively.

Appearance of the peaks due to Mn₂L₃⁺ and Mn₂L₃'⁺ ions can be explained with the help of the following reactions.

A quite intense peak at *m/z* 623 due to a similar specie [Mn₂(hnp)₃]⁺ has been noticed in all the complex. Furthermore, complex **I** shows a less intense peak due to [Mn₂(hpp)₃]⁺, whereas complex **II** exhibits comparatively sharp peak due to [Mn₂(bzac)₃]⁺ ion. Similarly, peaks due to [Mn₂(5-NO₂sal)₃]⁺ and [Mn₂(5-Brsal)₃]⁺ can be seen for complex **III** and **IV** respectively. High intensity of peak due to [Mn₂(bzac)₃]⁺ as compared to [Mn₂(hpp)₃]⁺, [Mn₂(5-NO₂sal)₃]⁺ and [Mn₂(5-Brsal)₃]⁺ indicates that the benzoylacetone is more strongly bounded to Mn^{II} than 2-hydroxypropiophenone, 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde and 5-bromosalicylaldehyde.

Thus, the mass spectral and other studies confirm the proposed structures of the complexes.

In vitro antibacterial screening : The free ligands and their metal complexes were tested against the bacterial species. Ciprofloxacin as a standard antibacterial agent

Table 2. Mass spectral data of mixed ligand complexes of Mn^{II} (*m/z* values and relative abundances)^a
m/z (relative abundance %)

Ions	[Mn(hnp)(hpp)] ⁺ (I)	[Mn(hnp)(bzac)] ⁺ (II)	[Mn(hnp)(5-NO ₂ sal)] ⁺ (III)	[Mn(hnp)(5-Brsal)] ⁺ (IV)
M ⁺	375 (2.77%)	387 (79.17%)	391 (8.57%)	426 (19.44%)
[M-Br] ⁺	-	-	-	346 (27.78%)
MnL ⁺	226 (22.22%)	226 (100%)	226 (77.14%)	226 (47.22%)
MnL' ⁺	204 (1.39%)	216 (94.44%)	221 (20%)	255 (27.78%)
MnL ₂ ⁺	397 (30.56%)	397 (25.00%)	397 (90%)	397 (23.61%)
MnL' ₂ ⁺	353 (5.56%)	377 (69.44%)	387 (8.57%)	455 (31.94%)
Mn ₂ L ₃ ⁺	623 (18.06%)	623 (15.28%)	623 (31.43%)	623 (16.67%)
Mn ₂ L' ₃ ⁺	557 (1.39%)	593 (22.22%)	608 (2.86%)	710 (16.67%)
[Mn ₂ L ₂ L'] ⁺	601 (5.56%)	613 (80.56%)	618 (8.57%)	652 (9.72%)
[Mn ₂ LL' ₂] ⁺	579 (0.28%)	603 (61.11%)	613 (5.71%)	681 (16.67%)

HL = 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (hnpH).

HL' = 2-Hydroxypropiophenone (hppH), benzoylacetone (bzacH), 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde (5-NO₂salH) or 5-bromosalicylaldehyde (5-BrsalH).

^aAll the fragments have been denoted as positive ions irrespective of whether they are odd electrons or even electrons species.

or reference was evaluated for their antibacterial activity and the result was compared with the free ligands and their metal complexes. The comparison of the biological activities of the synthesized compounds and known antibiotic shown the following results :

(i) Some free ligands and all the prepared metal complexes show positive effect towards *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Escherichia coli* strains.

(ii) The free ligands and complexes show higher antibacterial effect against *Staphylococcus aureus* than that of the standard. On the other hand, 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and [Mn(hnp)(Sal)(H₂O)₂] and [Mn(hnp)(hpp)(H₂O)₂] complexes are more potent bactericidal against *Escherichia coli* than standard^{32,33}.

(iii) The antibacterial screening data shows that the prepared metal chelates exhibit more inhibitory effects than the parent ligands. From the Table 3, it is clear that the zone of inhibition (bacteriostatic diameter) is much larger for metal complexes for bacterial strains. The increased activity of the metal chelates can be explained on the basis of overtone concept and Tweedy's chelation theory^{34,35}.

According to the chelation theory, the chelation tends to make the metal chelate act as more powerful and potent bactericidal agents, thus killing more of the bacteria than the ligands. It is observed that, in a complex, the positive charge of the metal is partially shared with the donor atoms present in the whole chelate ring. This in-

Table 3. Antimicrobial activity (zone of inhibition) of ligands and complexes

Sl. no.	Test compound	<i>E. coli</i> [Test zone of inhibition (mm)]	Ciprofloxacin [Control zone of inhibition (mm)]	<i>S. aureus</i> [Test zone of inhibition (mm)]	Ciprofloxacin [Control zone of inhibition (mm)]
1.	Salicylaldehyde	33	33	32	31
2.	2-Hydroxyacetophenone	No activity	30	No activity	31
3.	2-Hydroxypropiophenone	No activity	28	No activity	30
4.	2-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde	32	30	35.6	28
5.	5-Bromosalicylaldehyde	25	35	36	30
6.	[Mn(hnp)(sal)(H ₂ O) ₂]	33.6	26	42	30
7.	[Mn(hnp)(5-Brsal)(H ₂ O) ₂]	32	35	37	30
8.	[Mn(hnp)(hpp)(H ₂ O) ₂]	34.6	35	36	30
9.	[Mn(hnp)(hpp)(H ₂ O) ₂]	33	30	35.8	23

creases the lipophilic character of the metal chelate and favors its permeation through the lipid layer of the bacterial membranes and blocks the metal bonding sites on the enzymes of the micro-organism. These complexes also disturb the respiratory processes of the cell and thus block the synthesis of protein, which restricts further growth of the organism.

According to the overtone concept of cell permeability, the lipid membrane that surrounds the cell favors the passage of only lipid soluble material, due to which liposolubility is an important factor that controls the antibacterial activity.

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